

CHOOSING A TREATMENT METHOD FOR UNSATISFACTORY RESULTS CARDIODILATATION FOR PATIENTS WITH CARDIOSPASM AND ACHALASIA OF THE CARDIA

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Abstract. Among conservative methods of treatment, a special role is given to methods of instrumental influence. The aim is to study the results of various methods of cardiodylation in patients with cardiospasm and achalasia of the cardia. Material and methods. In the department of surgery of the esophagus and stomach of the State Institution "Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Surgery named after academician V. Vakhidov" from 1975 to 2018, 947 patients with cardiospasm and achalasia of the cardia were on outpatient and inpatient treatment. Results and discussions. The following minimally invasive treatment options were used. Dilation with the Stark apparatus was performed in 36 (3.8%) cases in the 70-80 years of the last century, but is not currently used due to injury. Conclusion. The reasons for the unsatisfactory results of minimally invasive methods of treatment of patients with achalasia of the cardia are the impossibility of dilation, failures in attempts to conduct the device through the cardia and directly unsatisfactory results of the course of expansion of the cardia.

Key words: cardiodylation; cardiospasm; achalasia of the cardia.

Relevance. Among conservative methods of treatment, a special role is given to methods of instrumental influence. During cardiodylation, violent tearing of the muscles of the cardia occurs with a decrease in the gradient of esophageal-gastric pressure, which improves the patency of food through the esophagus, i.e. the main symptom of the disease - dysphagia is eliminated. The number of good and satisfactory immediate results ranges from 75 to 90%. The issues of treatment tactics in case of unsatisfactory results of cardiodylation still remain controversial.

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Material and methods. In the department of surgery of the esophagus and stomach of the State Institution "Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Surgery named after academician V. Vakhidov" from 1975 to 2018, 947 patients with cardiospasm and achalasia of the cardia were on outpatient and inpatient treatment.

Results and discussions. The following minimally invasive treatment options were used. Dilation with the Stark apparatus was performed in 36 (3.8%) cases in the 70-80 years of the last century, but is not currently used due to injury. Preference is given to pneumatic – 829 (87.5%) and hydro-balloon - 61 (6.4%) dilation. Oesophageal augmentation with hollow boughs was performed in 7 (0.7%) patients only with stenosing reflux esophagitis, which developed after previously performed esophagocardiomyotomies. Good results of minimally invasive methods of treatment were noted in 606 (64%) patients, satisfactory – in 280 (29.5%), unsatisfactory – in 61 (6.4%).

Patients with unsatisfactory immediate results underwent extramucous esophagocardiomyotomy in various modifications (15); intraoperative dilation of the cardia (1); Marvedel-Wendel operation (1); resection of the cardia with the formation of esophagogastric anastomosis (2); extirpation of the esophagus with simultaneous plastic surgery (17). 25 patients refused surgery.

Conclusion. The reasons for the unsatisfactory results of minimally invasive methods of treatment of patients with achalasia of the cardia are the impossibility of dilation, failures in attempts to conduct the device through the cardia and directly unsatisfactory results of the course of expansion of the cardia. If cardiodilation is ineffective and impossible, surgical treatment is necessary, the operation option depends on the degree of neglect of the disease.

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